

Binding of Phenothiazine Drugs to Heptakis-Methylated β -Cyclodextrin Derivatives: Thermodynamics and Structure

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1 ABSTRACT

Experimental binding data from simple, well-defined model cases such as host-guest systems, are of value in testing and training computational models of noncovalent binding, such as those used in drug discovery. Cyclodextrins (CDs), macrocycles of glucose units, form a particularly accessible class of host molecules that are water-soluble and amenable to derivatization. CDs are used for pharmaceutical formulations and can even be drugs in their own right. We used calorimetry and NMR spectroscopy to characterize the noncovalent association of native β CD and three methylated derivatives of β CD with five phenothiazine drugs. The strongest association observed, that of thioridazine and one of the methyl derivatives, exceeds the affinity of rimantidine with β CD, while methylation at the 3 position of β CD abolished binding for all of the drugs studied. The variations in binding entropy and enthalpy across the dataset demonstrate a clear pattern of entropy-enthalpy compensation. The NMR data show that all of the drugs position at least one aromatic proton at the secondary face of the CD, and most also show evidence of deep penetration of the binding site. The results of this study were used in the SAMPL9 blinded binding affinity-prediction challenge.

2 INTRODUCTION

The ability to predict how chemical structure controls noncovalent binding is vital to drug discovery and supramolecular chemistry. Computational models can be used to map from structure to affinity, but even the most advanced methods are not yet accurate enough to circumvent the need for multiple cycles of experimental trial and error when seeking a potent ligand for a targeted protein in the early phases of a drug discovery project. Research aimed at enhancing the accuracy of computational methods has come

to rely more on experimental binding data obtained for well-defined, compact model cases, such as host-guest systems¹⁻⁶, which have been part of the SAMPL series of blinded prediction challenges since 2012⁷⁻¹³. Host-guest binding data can be used not only to test but also to train¹⁴ computational methods of predicting noncovalent binding affinities.

The cyclodextrins (CDs), macrocycles of glucose units, can be utilized as model binding systems and are of growing pharmaceutical interest in formulations and as drugs in their own right.^{2,3,15-17} The CDs are valuable model systems because they are readily available, water-soluble, and amenable to derivatization. The commonly studied CDs are rings of 6, 7, and 8 D-glucopyranose units, corresponding respectively to α -, β -, and γ -CD. Of these three, β -CD is perhaps the best characterized and can encapsulate a range of small molecules^{2,18,19}. The development of high-affinity CD derivatives and other hosts is of interest not only to generate diverse model systems for computational chemistry, but also to devise new medications that work by sequestering and thus in effect inactivating various drugs and toxins²⁰⁻²³. For example, the FDA approved drug sugammadex^{16,24} is a γ -CD derivative that binds the paralytic drugs rocuronium and vecuronium and consequently reverses paralysis in the post-surgery setting. Interestingly, sugammadex achieves this effect without reaching the low nanomolar-level dissociation constants normally associated with typical drugs; i.e., with drugs that work by binding a protein target. Instead, the dissociation constants of sugammadex with rocuronium and vecuronium are on the order of $0.1 \mu\text{M}$ ²¹.

One straightforward synthetic approach to the derivatization of cyclodextrins is to perfunctionalize one or more subsets of their three hydroxyl groups (Figure 1). In order of decreasing chemical reactivity, they are the primary hydroxyls, located at the smaller opening of the binding cavity; and the 2- and 3-hydroxyls, secondary hydroxyls situated at the larger opening²⁵. The most basic functionalization of hydroxyl groups is introduction of a methyl group to generate methoxy groups. Because of the order of reactivity, the three methylation patterns illustrated in Figure 1 – per-6-O-methyl, per-2,6-di-O-methyl, and per-2,3,6-tri-O-methyl, are particularly facile to access synthetically.

Figure 1. Structures of βCD , H6M- βCD , H26DM- βCD , and HTM- βCD .

Phenothiazine is a privileged bioactive scaffold, made up of a tricyclic aromatic unit with a thiazine center^{26,27}. It is present in multiple antipsychotic drugs, including promethazine (Phenergan) chlorpromazine (Thorazine), thioridazine (Mellaril), and trifluoperazine (Stelazine), and prochlorperazine (Compro). In addition, the phenothiazine drugs are toxic at high dose and there is no specific antidote for overdoses. CDs that bind phenothiazines well could thus be of interest as antidotes. However, little is known about how even the most straightforward CD derivatives interact with this class of drugs.

Here, we use a combination of isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and NMR spectroscopy to explore how three patterns of methylation influence the binding of five phenothiazine drugs by β CD. We consider the following four host molecules (Figure 1): native β -cyclodextrin (β CD), Heptakis-(6-O-Methyl)- β -cyclodextrin (H6M- β CD), Heptakis-(2,6-di-O-methyl)- β -cyclodextrin (H26DM- β CD), and Heptakis-(2,3,6-tri-O-methyl)- β -cyclodextrin (HTM- β CD). The phenothiazines studied (Table 1) are promazine (PMZ), promethazine (PMT), chlorpromazine (CPZ), thioridazine (TDZ), and trifluoperazine (TFP). The data reported here for β CD and H26DM- were used in the SAMPL9 blinded binding affinity-prediction challenge (<https://github.com/samplchallenges/SAMPL9>).

Table 1. Names, abbreviations, and structures of the five phenothiazine drugs studied here, along with computational estimates of selected chemical properties from Drugbank²⁸. Protonation states shown are those expected at pH 7.4.

Drug Name (abbreviation)	Structure	Estimated chemical Properties	
		pKa	log p
Promazine HCl (PMZ)		9.4	4.5
Promethazine HCl (PMT)		9.1	4.3
Chlorpromazine HCl (CPZ)		9.2	4.5
Thioridazine HCl (TDZ)		8.9	5.5
Trifluoperazine 2 HCl (TFP)		8.0	4.7

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS

The phenothiazines, HTM- β CD, and H26DM- β CD were purchased from Sigma Life Sciences; β CD was obtained from Alfa Aesar; and H6M- β CD was purchased from The Cyclodextrin Shop. All compounds were used without further purification. All solutions were prepared by weight in buffer or D₂O for calorimetry and NMR, respectively.

3.2 ISOTHERMAL TITRATION CALORIMETRY (ITC) EXPERIMENTS

All ITC measurements were run in triplicate on a Microcal ITC200 in 25mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.4, at 25 °C with a 20-point binding isotherm (1-1.5 μ L injections). A single cyclodextrin stock solution was drawn from, but a fresh drug solution was prepared for each replicate.

In each case, the guest was in the cell and the host in the syringe. The concentrations of the solutions were tailored for each complex, based on binding affinity, to obtain appropriate C values²⁹. Guest concentrations ranged between 200 and 500 μ M and host concentrations ranged between 7 and 10 mM. The raw data were analyzed with Microcal Data Analyzer in Origin 7.

3.3 NMR

¹H- and 2D NOESY NMR spectra of all phenothiazine-cyclodextrin complexes were collected at 298 K on a 600 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrometer fitted with a 1.7 mm triple resonance cryoprobe with z-axis gradients. All NMR studies were run in D₂O. ¹H-NMR was collected with F1 presaturation of the water peak with 16 scans, and 2D NOESY spectra were performed using water suppression and excitation sculpting with gradient and States-TPPI acquisition mode.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 BINDING THERMODYNAMICS

We used ITC to determine the binding free energy, enthalpy, and entropy, of five phenothiazine-based drugs with β CD and two methylated derivatives, H6M- β CD and H26DM- β CD, under uniform conditions of temperature and buffer. Interestingly, no binding was detected between any of the phenothiazines and the third derivative, HTM- β CD. The remaining results are summarized in Tables 2-4 and Figure 2, and the Supporting Information provides the experimental details, such as enthalpograms, results of individual titrations, and concentrations used.

4.1.1 Binding Affinities

Across all systems studied, the measured dissociation constants range up to 820 μ M (β CD with PMT) and down to 18 μ M (H26DM- β CD with TDZ). In fact, TDZ binds all three hosts more tightly than any of the other guest molecules. Overall, methylation at the 2 and 6 positions has only modest effects on affinity, as the maximum changes relative to native β CD are only about four-fold across both CD derivatives and all guests. In contrast, as noted above, 3-methylation destroys binding in all cases. Going

from native β CD to H6M- β CD produces small, mixed effects on affinity; the greatest drop in K_d , which occurs for TDZ, is only two-fold. Going from native β CD to H26DM- β CD leads in all cases to either an improvement in affinity or an essentially unchanged affinity, with the greatest improvement observed for PMT. Promazine and chlorpromazine differ only in the replacement of a hydrogen by a chlorine. Across all three hosts, chlorpromazine binds more tightly than promazine, with a maximal 4.6x increase in the case of H6M- β CD.

Rimantidine is known as one of the tighter-binding guests of β CD, with a measured dissociation constant of $\sim 30 \mu\text{M}$ ^{30,31}. Thus, it is of interest that TDZ and β CD come close to this affinity ($66 \mu\text{M}$), and that TDZ and H26DM- β CD actually surpass it ($18 \mu\text{M}$).

In our prior study of rimantidine and methylcyclohexanol binding to β CD and β CDs mono-derivatized at the 3 and 6 hydroxyls, we observed that derivatization at 3 always weakened binding, while derivatization at the 6 position largely preserved it³⁰. This result is broadly consistent with our present observation that persubstitution at 3 eliminates binding, while derivatization at 6 leaves it largely unchanged. Although there is no guarantee that similar results will be observed for other guests or cyclodextrin substituents, it would appear that efforts aimed at boosting the affinity of cyclodextrins for various guests will tend to be more productive if they avoid modifying the 3 hydroxyl site.

4.1.2 Binding Enthalpies and Entropies

The standard binding free energies across all host-guest systems with detectable binding range over 10 kJ/mol. As commonly observed, however, the binding enthalpies range much more widely, from -38.3 kJ/mol to -12.6 kJ/mol. The change in enthalpy favors binding in all cases, though. The small range of the binding free energy and the large range of the binding enthalpy imply the presence of entropy-enthalpy compensation within the dataset. This is illustrated in Figure 3, where the present data are displayed along with those from a prior ITC study from our lab.

Figure 2. Thermodynamic signatures of binding for β CD (top), H6M- β CD (middle), and H26DM- β CD (bottom). See Table 1 for guest name abbreviations.

Table 2. Binding measurements for β CD with phenothiazine drugs. N: fitted host-guest binding stoichiometry. K_a : association constant. K_d : dissociation constant = $1/K_a$. ΔG : standard free energy of binding ($-RT \ln K_a$). ΔH : standard enthalpy of binding. ΔS : standard entropy of binding. Units as listed. All results are means of triplicate measurements. Uncertainties are standard errors of the mean across the triplicate measurements.

Guest	N	K_a (M^{-1})	K_d (μM)	ΔG (kJ/mol)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (kJ/K/mol)
PMZ	1.1 \pm 0.01	4440 \pm 90	225 \pm 5	-20.8 \pm 0.1	-24.8 \pm 0.3	-13.2 \pm 1
PMT	0.94 \pm 0.03	1900 \pm 90	525 \pm 30	-18.7 \pm 0.1	-16.5 \pm 0.8	7.6 \pm 3
CPZ	0.77 \pm 0.01	9390 \pm 190	107 \pm 2	-22.7 \pm 0.1	-26.0 \pm 0.5	-11.1 \pm 3
TDZ	1.1 \pm 0.1	15100 \pm 400	66 \pm 2	-23.9 \pm 0.1	-20.6 \pm 0.5	10.8 \pm 2
TFP	1.2 \pm 0.1	5100 \pm 300	196 \pm 10	-21.2 \pm 0.1	-16.3 \pm 1.0	16.3 \pm 4

Table 3. Binding measurements for H6M- β CD with phenothiazine drugs. See 2 for details.

Guest	N	K_a (M^{-1})	K_d (μM)	ΔG (kJ/mol)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (kJ/K/mol)
PMZ	1.2 \pm 0.1	2700 \pm 400	380 \pm 50	-19.9 \pm 0.2	-20.2 \pm 2	-1. \pm 8
PMT	0.79 \pm 0.05	1220 \pm 50	820 \pm 40	-17.6 \pm 0.1	-24.7 \pm 2	-24 \pm 8
CPZ	0.62 \pm 0.02	12100 \pm 700	83 \pm 5	-23.3 \pm 0.2	-12.6 \pm 0.6	36 \pm 2
TDZ	1.2 \pm 0.03	31200 \pm 1000	32 \pm 1	-25.7 \pm 0.1	-29.4 \pm 0.5	-13 \pm 2
TFP	1.0 \pm 0.06	7700 \pm 600	130 \pm 10	-22.2 \pm 0.2	-22.8 \pm 1	-2 \pm 5

Table 4. Binding measurements for H26DM- β CD with phenothiazine drugs. See Table 2 for details.

Guest	N	K_a (M^{-1})	K_d (μM)	ΔG (kJ/mol)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (kJ/K/mol)
PMZ	0.99 \pm 0.01	5080 \pm 90	197 \pm 3	-21.2 \pm 0.05	-21.4 \pm 0.1	-0.9 \pm 0.3
PMT	1.1 \pm 0.03	8420 \pm 90	119 \pm 1	-22.4 \pm 0.03	-17.0 \pm 0.1	18.2 \pm 0.2
CPZ	0.77 \pm 0.01	9100 \pm 300	110 \pm 3	-22.6 \pm 0.08	-25.0 \pm 0.4	-7.9 \pm 0.3
TDZ	0.87 \pm 0.01	54900 \pm 2000	18 \pm 0.6	-27.1 \pm 0.09	-38.3 \pm 0.2	-37.8 \pm 0.8
TFP	0.56 \pm 0.04	11500 \pm 400	87 \pm 3	-23.2 \pm 0.09	-31.1 \pm 2	-26. \pm 7

Figure 3. Entropy-enthalpy compensation plot. Each point is one host-guest pair. Colored points are new data from this study and are colored according to the host compound. Gray-scale points, provided for context, are data from our prior study³⁰, which studied the guests rimantidine and trans-methylcyclohexanol across multiple β CD derivatives; these are shaded by guest compound. The radius of each data point is proportional to the measured standard free energy of binding.

4.2 HOST-GUEST INTERACTIONS VIA 2D NOESY NMR

Both the guests and the hosts studied here are asymmetric, so their bound complexes might adopt any of a number of conformations, defined, for example, by the positioning of the guests' bulky, tricyclic phenothiazine moieties and their cationic side chains within the binding site. We used two-dimensional NOESY NMR studies of the host-guest complexes to identify pairs of host and guest atoms that reside close enough (less than about 6 Å) to be detectable as an NOE cross-peak. This information provides insight into the nature of the complexes and can be used as an additional check of computer models. Note that contacts which are too short-lived do not generate observable NOEs, so the list of close contacts inferred by these studies may not be comprehensive. The spectra of all the host-guest complexes studied are provided in the Supporting Information.

Every complex studied here, except for one where no NOEs at all were observed, has NOEs between at least one aromatic guest proton (G1-G9 in Figure 4. Numbering of atoms used to identify NOEs in Tables 5-7) and the hydrogen of the CD's H3 carbon (H3 in Figure 4. Numbering of atoms used to identify NOEs in Tables 5-7.) Thus, in all cases, at least part of the phenothiazine moiety is at the secondary face of the CD. In most complexes, there are also NOEs between aromatic guest protons and the CD's H5, signifying that part of the phenothiazine moiety penetrates deep into the host's cavity. The drugs TDZ and TFP show additional NOEs that involve the cationic ends of their side-chains. These NOEs consistently involve H6 or HMe1 on the host, meaning that the cationic side chains lie at the primary face of the hosts. We conjecture that the cationic side chains of all of the phenothiazines studied here reside at the primary face, but that only the relatively bulky side-chains of TDZ and TFP are sufficiently locked in to generate observable NOEs.

Figure 4. Numbering of atoms used to identify NOEs in Tables 5-7.

Table 5. Observed NOEs in phenothiazine- β CD complexes. Atom notation is provided in Figure 4.

Guest	NOEs Observed
PMZ	3.423-7.313 (H3-G8 & 2)
PMT	3.619 – 7.265 (H5 – G7) 3.619 – 7.045 (H5 – G9) 3.759 – 7.044 (H3 – G9)
CPZ	3.806- 7.401-7.343(H5-G8, 6, 4, & 2) 3.806- 7.219-7.209(H5-G3 & 7) 3.853 – 4.378- H3-G11a 3.806 – 4.282- H3-G11b
TDZ	3.712- 7.357-7.331 (H5-G2 & 3) 3.712- 7.357-7.331 (H5-G2 & 3) 3.759 – 6.928 ((H3 – G9) 3.712 – 6.900 (H5 – G7) 3.853 – 2.468 (H6 – GMeS

TFP	3.622 - 7.479 (H5-G2) 3.763- 7.480 (H3-G2) 3.853 – 2.468 (H6 – G20)
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Table 6. Observed NOEs in phenothiazine-H6M- β CD complexes.

Guest	NOEs Observed
PMZ	3.712 – 7.313 (H5 – G4 & 6) 3.712 – 7.152 (H5 – G1 & 9)
PMT	3.776 – 7.377 (H3 – G3 &7) 3.776 – 7.339 (H3 – G6 & 4) 3.776 – 7.201 (H3 – G1 & 9)
CPZ	3.745 – 7.375 (H3 – G3) 3.745 – 7.217 (H3 – G1) 3.698 – 7.217 (H5 – G1) 3.698 – 7.270 (H5 – G6) 3.698 – 7.146 (H5 – G4) 3.698 – 7.051 (H5 – G9)
TDZ	3.700 – 7.236 (H5 – G1) 3.700 – 6.902 (H5 – G7) 3.746 – 7.356 (H3 – G4 &6) 3.746 – 7.270 (H3 – G6) 3.746 – 6.915 (H3 – G7) 3.746 – 6.870 (H3 – G9)
TFP	3.722 – 7.263(H5 – G1) 3.722 – 7.492 (H5 – G2) 3.722 – 7.276(H5- G6) 3.722 – 7.158(H5 – G9) 3.769 – 7.170 (H3 – G9) 3.769 – 4.204 (H3 – G11)

Table 7. Observed NOEs phenothiazine-H26DM- β CD complexes.

Guest	NOEs Observed
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PMZ	3.712 – 7.270 – 7.259(H3 – G6 &4) 3.572 – 7.096 (HMe ₂ – G3&7)
PMT	No NOE Observed
CPZ	3.723- 7.228 (H3 – G6) 3.723- 7.004 (H3 – G9)
TDZ	3.712- 7.276 (H3 – G6) 3.712 – 6.625 (H3 -G9) 3.385 - 2.480 (HMe ₁ – GMeS)
TFP	3.590 - 7.104 (H3-G7 & 9) 3.590 – 2.935 (H6 – G20)

5 CONCLUSIONS

We used ITC and NMR to study the interactions of five phenothiazine drugs with native β CD and three β CD derivatives, permethylated at the 6 position, the 2 and 6 positions, and the 2, 3, and 6 positions. The resulting data will be of use to test and train computational models and binding, and indeed have already been used in the SAMPL9 blinded affinity-prediction challenge. Notable observations include the following.

1. Permethylation at the 3 position of β CD eliminates detectable binding of the phenothiazines.
2. Permethylation at the 2 and 6 positions leads to up to 4-fold stronger binding of some of these guest molecules.
3. TDZ is consistently the strongest binder, with a dissociation constant as low as 18 μ M in the case of H26DM- β CD, surpassing that of rimantidine with native β CD.
4. Chlorpromazine binds consistently more strongly than promazine, with a K_d nearly 5-fold lower in the case of H6M- β CD.
5. The enthalpy of binding is strongly favorable in all cases, and the thermodynamic data fall on a classic entropy-enthalpy compensation line.
6. 2D NMR studies show that all guests position at least one aromatic proton at the secondary face of the CD in all cases, and most also have NOEs to H5, indicate deep penetration of the binding site.
7. TDZ and TFP have additional NOEs between their cationic side-chains and protons at the primary face.

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7 SUPPORTING INFORMATION

1. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-ITC-complexes.xlsx: Results of analysis of ITC data for triplicate runs for each host-guest system, Host and guest SMILES strings, and binding thermodynamic summary.
2. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-ITC-Raw-Data.zip: compressed file with numerical data from the ITC runs.
3. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-Enthalpograms.pptx: Images of combined enthalpogram for each cyclodextrin-phenothiazine pair.
4. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-2DNMR-BCD.pptx: 2D NMR spectra of β -cyclodextrin and phenothiazine complexes
5. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-2DNMR-H6MBCD.pptx: 2D NMR Heptakis-(2,6-di-methyl)- β -cyclodextrin and phenothiazine complexes
6. SAMPL9-Andrade-Chen-Gilson-2DNMR-H26DMBCD.pptx: 2D NMR Heptakis-(2,6-di-methyl)- β -cyclodextrin and phenothiazine complexes

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